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Abstract. This article covers important issues of comprehensive intellectual development of elementary school students, information about the harmony and commonality of the concepts of "intellect" and "thinking". The importance of the elements of personality development and the development of intellectual abilities in students of all subjects in primary school programs is considered.

Key words: Primary education, intellect, memory, ability, intellectual, philosophy, thinking, socio-psychological, talent.

РАЗВИТИЕ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Абстрактный. В данной статье освещены важные вопросы всестороннего интеллектуального развития учащихся младших классов, информация о гармонии и общности понятий «интеллект» и «мышление». Рассмотрена важность элементов развития личности и развития интеллектуальных способностей у учащихся всех предметов в программах начальной школы.

Ключевые слова: Начальное образование, интеллект, память, способности, интеллектуальные, философия, мышление, социально-психологические, талант.

“A person who cannot perfect himself cannot ensure the perfection of others.” **Confucius**

Today, various approaches to improving the quality of education are proposed and implemented in practice. One of the modern approaches to the educational process is the creative approach. As we know, terms such as creativity and creativity are widely used in school practice. In the pedagogical and psychological literature, it is defined as follows. “Creativity is a product of the intellect, embodied through a motivational structure. This structure slows down or stimulates its manifestation.” As a “unit of research” of creative expressions of a person, psychologists see intellectual activity, which combines mental abilities and personal factors. Studying the problem of the typology of intellectual activity and creativity, we see that there is an optimal and argued position on the issue of levels of intellectual activity and their correlation with creativity. According to our scientists who have conducted research in the field of pedagogy in the world, a 7-8-year-old child usually thinks in certain categories. Then, there is a transition to the stage of formal operations, which is associated with a certain level of development of the ability to generalize and abstract. By the

time schoolchildren enter the 5th grade, they should learn to think independently, draw conclusions, compare, analyze, find the specific and the general, and establish patterns. However, this is often not observed. Because children find such actions as generalization, comparison, analysis, and drawing conclusions difficult. In this regard, children lose interest in science and the study of various phenomena. Passive perception and assimilation of new things cannot be the basis of solid knowledge.

If we take the primary education system of the French Republic, one of the countries that stands out in terms of the quality of education and meets world standards, as an example, French children are required to start school at the age of six. The duration of study at this school level is 5 years. The first year is an adaptation year, the next two children go to primary grades, and then to secondary grades. This is how the principle of gradual complication of educational material and smooth adaptation of students to new conditions and educational tasks works in primary schools in France. In junior schools in France operating according to this schedule, Saturday is also a school day, but classes are held only in the first half of the day. On weekdays, children are at school from 9:00 to 17:00, but classes have a two-hour break from 12:00 to 14:00, when they can relax in the fresh air and play with friends. Primary - from 6 to 11 years old - 5 years of study in primary school. During this time, children learn the basics of classical school subjects and learn to clearly plan their daily routine. The morning of a primary school student (L'école élémentaire) begins with a trip to the library. 15 minutes before the lesson, children line up to exchange their read books for new ones. All library books are marked with colorful stickers and divided into 12 blocks. For example, books marked with pink stickers are for those who have just learned to read. And books of the most difficult level are marked with striped stickers. This allows the teacher to easily understand what level the student is at.

Nowadays, only educated, modern, independent-thinking, intellectually developed, highly qualified specialists in their profession can ensure the great future of the country.

Intellect (Latin: intellectus - to know, understand, perceive) is a person's mental ability; the ability to accurately reflect and transform life, the environment in the mind, to think, read and learn, to know the world and accept social experience; The ability to solve various problems, come to a decision, act rationally, and foresee events. Intelligence includes perception, memory, thinking, and speech.

We can distinguish three qualitative levels of intellectual activity: motivated-productive; heuristic; creative. At the same time, the first level corresponds to the concept of "general talent". The second level is heuristic, when a person, having a sufficiently reliable solution method, "continues to analyze the composition, structure of his activity, compares individual tasks with each other. This leads to the discovery of new, original, much more intelligent than the first appearance of solutions".

The highest level of intellectual activity is considered to be the creative level. At this level, the law identified by a person becomes not a formal method, but an independent problem. Adhering to this position, we recognize the fact that two fundamentally different levels of creativity correspond to two types of thinking - empirical and theoretical. The typology of creativity is also based on this classification of levels of intellectual activity. At the motivated-productive level, people are capable of solid hypotheses and original discoveries.

The second level - heuristic - is suitable for discovering new laws empirically, while the creative level is proportional to theoretical discoveries. Taking as a basis the idea that creativity manifests the quality of an integrative personality, we will analyze the components of

creativity.

Today, in our country, major changes are being made to the school education system based on the idea that "New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold." It is necessary to carry out work aimed at developing the intellectual thinking of primary school students. It should be remembered that the process of developing logical thinking should be carried out comprehensively and systematically. Such work can be carried out not only in the classroom, but also in extracurricular activities. The main task of teachers in this type of activity is to competently select various forms and methods that are convenient and acceptable for young children. Interactive methods are also important in that the teacher never sharply rejects the student's idea, but only in time suggests the correct conclusion. As a result, the student will understand his/her own mistakes. This will prevent them from becoming discouraged and the possible defects in thinking that may arise due to this discouragement. Interactive methods are based on mutual respect between the student and the teacher. Currently, there are many modern teaching methods. Among these methods, we can say that the "interactive" method is the most widely used and most effective method. Because this method can effectively influence the intellectual abilities of primary school students. At the same time, the term "interactive" is actually derived from the English word "interactive", which means "mutual influence" and refers to the mutual discussion, thinking-based activity or joint solution in an activity or method.

The opportunities for developing students' intellectual abilities through primary school mathematics lessons are wider than in other subjects. This is because we implement interdisciplinary integration by simply solving a problem in a mathematics lesson, and we help students to relate broader theoretical knowledge to practical life, and in mathematics lessons students also become aware of the changes taking place in their lives.

The authors of the theory of mental development distinguish the following stages of the formation of intellectual learning:

- 1) the stage characterized by the identification of experience in the application of learning;
- 2) diagnostic stage, in which the levels of formation of the studies are determined;
- 3) motivation stage;
- 4) stage of understanding the algorithm for using the method;
- 5) stage of direct application and comparison with other subjects.

Two active learning theories have gained wide application in teaching schoolchildren to think: representatives of the first school developed the theory of the formation and development of intellectual operations. The main idea of this theory is as follows: the assimilation of knowledge occurs by students only as a result of the implementation of a certain system of efforts. The action is functionally connected with the object being performed on it, includes the goal of changing this object and the means of such change. All this together constitutes the executive part of the action being formed. To organize the primary education process on the basis of pedagogical technologies, a new approach to education, innovative educational technologies, should be based more on the activity of learners, aimed at developing

their need and skills for independent learning. The teacher must move from the role of a knowledge transmitter to the role of organizing the active learning process of learners, managing their motivation and activities for learning, rationally supporting and developing their existing needs for knowledge, free thinking, creativity, and innovation in psychological and pedagogical terms. At each stage of the innovation process, participants in this process must work in the following three areas: material and technical; organizational; socio-psychological. The introduction of any innovation, including the introduction of pedagogical technology, and its necessary effect depend on how the members of the pedagogical team perceive the innovation and their attitude to it.

In developing the intellectual abilities of primary school students

1. Non-standard problems
2. Logical problems
3. We will achieve our goal if we make wider use of problem types that lead to problematic situations.

The development of the abilities of primary school students is an important part of the pedagogical process.

With the help of a teacher, students should learn to think, highlight the main thing, analyze different facts and points of view, compare and contrast them, ask questions and try to independently find answers to them. Active daily activity is necessary for the development of the student's personality. We need to create conditions for young students to acquire knowledge, and then new inventions and innovations will appear in our country.

Conclusion. We consider the main direction of developing the memory of junior schoolchildren to be the formation of indirect memorization, that is, the use of auxiliary means for memorization, including signs and symbols. This requires the ability to divide the memorized objects into parts, highlight various features in them, establish certain connections and relationships between each of them and a certain system of traditional signs. To develop thinking, I use the following exercises: "additional object", "grouping", etc. One of the important features of verbal-logical thinking is the functioning of concepts. The development of verbal-logical thinking involves the formation of mental operations: analysis, synthesis, generalization, etc. To develop comparative operations, I use tasks in which we need to compare similar objects (fly and butterfly; table and chair; book and notebook; water and milk, etc.) and ask them to name the signs of similarity and difference. We consider the formation of positive motivation for the process of educational and cognitive activity and intellectual tension to be one of the main tasks. I try to ensure the emergence of positive emotions in the learning process. In this case, the deep inner experiences of the individual are connected with cognitive processes (attention, memory, memorization, understanding), making the process of developing intellectual abilities more effective.

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